

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATING LESSONS IN TEACHING GERMAN AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE: TIPS AND IDEAS

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ABSTRACT

In the article were analyzed the motivating lessons in teaching German as foreign language. Tips and ideas are given

Entry into classes has enormous potential: They can activate the students' willingness to learn, motivate them and awaken their spirit of discovery. You can find out how to do this and what you should be aware of here. We provide five specific ideas for a successful start in the second class. The start of lessons - often underestimated. Successful lessons can be much more than just the prelude to the following 45 or 90 minutes: They can act as "appetizers" and make the students want to take part in the lesson. They can make it easier to arrive at the lesson and arouse the willingness to learn. You can clear your head for new topics, motivate and arouse interest. You can spark enthusiasm for a topic and arouse the spirit of discovery. Good entry points: functions and requirements

MAIN PART

At the beginning of a one-to-one lesson or at the start of a new lesson, the start of the lesson can effectively introduce the students to a new topic. Introducing the topic, goals and course of the lesson can also provide orientation and give students an idea of where the journey should go. He can also show the connections to topics that have already been worked on or future topics - and thus link old and new knowledge.

For all of this to work, you need to pick up the students from where they are. In addition, when choosing a method, you should always consider the specific situation in the particular learning group. The group dynamics is an important factor for the question of which method works and makes sense in the respective class. Not every entry suits every group. The start of

the lesson that you choose should ideally also reflect the individual knowledge, experience, abilities and skills as well as the strengths of the students. In this way, you can leverage previously unused potential. Make sure that the start of the lesson is actually comprehensible for all students - so you have to find a common denominator even with heterogeneous learning groups.

Methods of arrival. Your students and you yourself have to arrive at the lesson first. If you are still thinking about the last lesson, have been annoyed during the break and are still grumbling to yourself or have to hurry in such a way that you are completely out of breath, you will find it difficult to get involved in the following lesson. A pleasant learning environment and a clear head are crucial for learning success.

Start by uncovering motivation killers and specifically questioning your weaker self. For this purpose, give students aged 14 and over a worksheet on which they should write down what is slowing their motivation. They should not read the result aloud, but think about ways to increase their motivation. An example could be: "I don't feel like doing math today. But I plan to report at least three times and after the lesson I'll buy myself a chocolate bar at the kiosk." It is important that the students themselves find possible solutions for their "motivational brakes". This is the only way they can actually overcome their inner weaker self.

Alternatively, you can also start with the "current hour", for example. You can read a current newspaper clipping, show a photo or simply bring up a topic that is currently being widely discussed in the media. Ask students what they know about

it and how they think about it, but if necessary, let them simply express concern. Current topics often move the students very strongly - from the age of 10 they can express themselves well in the classroom.

Thematic motivation ideas

So that you can motivate the students for the specific topic, they must first become familiar with it. Ideally, you awaken the students' "instinct" so that they develop questions of their own accord and want to investigate the matter.

For classes with students aged 10 and over, you can start as a storyteller, for example: you tell a short story, an anecdote or even a fairy tale to introduce the topic of the lesson. The key message and the background to the story can then be examined in more detail in the following lesson. In every subject there are famous personalities - for example Albert Einstein, Franz Kafka or Marie Curie - to whom you can contribute exciting anecdotes. Make sure, however, that you are actually telling the story and not just reading it - that makes the story livelier and more impressive.

Alternatively, you can start with a demonstration to show students an abstract content through objects or media. The more senses you address, the better - the students should dare to see, hear, smell, taste and / or feel the matter.

If you'd rather start with a worksheet instead of using demonstrations straight away, think about a couple of exciting lies for once: Students aged 10 and over can hand out an introductory text on the topic of the lesson. In it you name a lot of interesting facts, but not all of them are true - some are exaggerated, others are

simply wrong. The students now become active as detectives: they have to find out which of the statements are true and which are not. To do this, they do their own research in the appropriate source of information, for example in textbooks, specialist books, encyclopedias or on the Internet. The solutions are then discussed together.

You should take inner barriers seriously and not just ignore them - this applies to both your students and your own inner attitude. Not every entry suits you and not every method suits your class. So keep observing how your students and yourself

feel about the start of the lesson and whether or how they work. Start with what you feel confident about and stay open to new ideas. Because only when you have tried something do you know whether you and your students like it.

CONCLUSION

With the activities that are easy to use, you will quickly be able to quickly pep up your tired or demotivated students for language lessons.

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